

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part-XXI. Synthesis of Thiazolidinone and their Derivatives from 4-[*S*-(Benzo-thiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetyl]thiosemicarbazides

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4-[*S*-(Benzo-thiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetyl]thiosemicarbazides (**2**; R=H and C₆H₅) were synthesised from 1-[*S*-(benzo-thiazolyl-2')]mercaptomethylhydrazide (**1**) by reacting with potassium thiocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate respectively. The thiosemicarbazides afforded thiazolidinones (**4a** and **5a**) through different routes. The thiazolidinones furnished arylidene derivatives (**4b** and **5b**) with aromatic aldehydes and aminomethyl compounds (**6**) through Mannich reactions. The structure of the compounds are established using spectral and analytical data.

THE thiazolidinones possessing heterocyclic moieties as the substituent¹ and several other aromatic system² possess significant bactericidal and fungicidal activities³. In one of our previous communications⁴ on benzothiazolylthiazolidinones, the thiazolidinone ring is linked to benzothiazolo moiety through an imino function. Therefore, it was considered of interest to introduce benzothiazole moiety through mercaptomethylene and mercaptomethylene-carbamido functionalities to the thiazolidinone ring in the same position and make a comparative study of their antimicrobial behaviour. The *S*-(benzo-thiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetylhydrazide (**1**), used as the starting material, is prepared from ethyl ester of benzothiazolylmercaptoacetic acid. The hydrazide afforded 4-[*S*-(benzo-thiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetyl]-thiosemicarbazide (**2**; R=H) and 4-[*S*-(benzo-thiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetyl]-1-phenylthiosemicarbazide (**2**; R=C₆H₅) after the reaction with potassium thiocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate respectively. The disubstituted thiosemicarbazide (**2**; R=C₆H₅) when condensed with monochloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in acetic acid gave the thiazolidinone (**4a**) as colourless crystalline solid.

The assignment of its structure as **4a** was confirmed since hydrolysis of the compound with boiling alcoholic HCl gave 3-phenyl-2,4-thiazolidinone along with the original hydrazide (**1**). The monosubstituted thiosemicarbazide (**2**; R=H) underwent cyclisation to give 2-mercapto-5-[*S*-(benzo-thiazolyl-2')]mercaptomethyl-1,3,4-*s*-triazole (**3**) after reaction with 2*N* NaOH solution, from which the thiazolidinone (**5**) was isolated as pale yellow needles after reacting with monochloroacetic acid in ethanol. The arylidene derivatives (**4b**, **4c**, **5b** and **5c**) of the two thiazolidinones are prepared by condensing the thiazolidinones with aromatic aldehydes in acetic acid. The amino-

a, X=2H, b, X=C₆H₅CH=,
c, X=*p*-Cl-C₆H₄CH=, d, R'=CH₃,
e, R'=C₂H₅

alkyl derivatives of **5a** are also prepared by reacting the thiazolidinones with formaldehyde and various secondary amines in HCl.

The ir spectra of **4a** gave a slightly broad band centered at 1720 cm⁻¹ for the amidic carbonyl group of the thiazolidinone ring and the side chain. A similar broad band with a bathochromic shift at 1680 cm⁻¹ was found in its benzylidene compound (**4b**). The mercaptotriazole (**3**) gave a broad band at 3400–3200 cm⁻¹ (NH) and a weak band at 2750 cm⁻¹ (SH). These bands were absent in the thiazolidinone (**5a**) prepared from **3** and a new peak for carbonyl at 1710 cm⁻¹ appeared which underwent a bathochromic shift to 1680 cm⁻¹ in its benzylidene derivative (**5b**).

Biological activity: The thiazolidinones and their derivatives were screened against *S. aureus* by agar plate diffusion technique⁵ and *A. niger* by spore germination method. The compounds **4a**, **5a**, **4b** and **5b** inhibited the spore germination in a concentration of 10 ppm whereas none of the compounds show any bactericidal potency against

S. aureus. Thus the introduction of sulphur atom augmented the fungicidal activity as compared to the compounds reported earlier⁴.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

Ethyl-S-(benzothiazole-2')mercaptoacetate: A mixture of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (5.01 g, 10 mmol), ethyl chloroacetate (4.5 ml, 12 mmol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (2 g) in dry acetone (25 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 1 h. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the solvent evaporated. The oily residue was cooled in the refrigerator overnight and the resulting solids were recrystallised from ethanol (4 g, 53.7%), m.p. 32° (Found: S, 25.27. $C_{11}H_{11}N_1S_2O_2$ requires: S, 25.29%).

1-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')]mercaptomethylhydrazide (1): A solution of the above ester (2.5 g) and hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed slowly on a water-bath for 30 min. After cooling, the hydrazide deposited as colourless needles was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (2 g, 85%), m.p. 160° (Found: S, 26.71. $C_9H_9N_3OS_2$ requires: S, 26.77%).

4-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetyl]thiosemicarbazide (2) (R=H): A mixture of **1** (2.39 g, 10 mmol), potassium thiocyanate (1.94 g, 20 mmol) in concentrated HCl (10 ml) and water (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and then cooled. The resulting colourless solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol (2 g, 67.9%), m.p. 177–78° (Found: S, 32.16. $C_{10}H_{10}N_4OS_2$ requires: S, 32.21%); ν_{max} 3 450–3 300br (NH), 1 740 (C=O), 1 625 and 1 590 cm^{-1} .

4-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetyl]-1-phenylthiosemicarbazide (2) (R=C₆H₅): A solution of **1** (2.1 g) and phenylisothiocyanate (1.4 g) in rectified spirit (25 ml), was refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. After cooling, the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (1.7 g, 53%), m.p. 157° (Found: S, 25.60. $C_{16}H_{14}N_4OS_2$ requires: S, 25.66%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 250br (NH), 1 730 (C=O) and 1 600 cm^{-1} .

2-Mercapto-5-[S-benzothiazolyl-2']mercaptomethyl-1,3,4-s-triazole (3): The thiocarbazine (**2**) (R=H; 2.98 g) was refluxed in 2N NaOH solution (30 ml) for 3 h. After cooling the insoluble material was filtered off. The filtrate on acidification with glacial acetic acid gave a solid which was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (1.9 g, 68%), m.p. 194° (Found: S, 34.3. $C_{10}H_8N_4S_3$ requires: S, 34.28%); ν_{max} 3 400–3 200br (NH) and 2 750 cm^{-1} (SH).

2-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetamido]imino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (4a): A mixture of **2** (R=C₆H₅; 2.5 g, 6 mmol), monochloroacetic acid

(0.66 g, 7 mmol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was evaporated, cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with hot water and recrystallised from ethanol (1.56 g, 56.5%), m.p. 172° (Found: S, 23.16. $C_{18}H_{14}N_4O_2S_3$ requires: S, 23.18%); ν_{max} 3 300br (NH) and 1 720br cm^{-1} (two C=O).

2-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')mercaptoacetamido]imino-5-benzylidene-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (4b): A mixture of **4a** (2 g, 4 mmol), benzaldehyde (0.5 g, 4 mmol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed slowly over direct flame for 4 h. It was then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (1.3 g, 54%), m.p. 188° (Found: S, 19.14. $C_{22}H_{18}N_4S_3O_2$ requires: S, 19.12%); ν_{max} 3 350br (NH), 1 700 (C=O) and 1 600 cm^{-1} .

The 5-(*p*-chloro)benzylidene derivative (**4c**) was prepared from **4a** (0.5 g) and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.15 g) by following the above procedure and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 182° (Found: S, 17.90. $C_{22}H_{17}N_4S_3O_2Cl$ requires: S, 17.89%); ν_{max} 3 400br (NH), 1 690 (C=O) and 1 590 cm^{-1} .

3-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')mercaptomethyl]thiazolo[2,3-c]-s-triazol-5(6H)-one (5a): A mixture of **3** (2.98 g, 10 mmol), monochloroacetic acid (1.13 g, 12 mmol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was then distilled off and residue was filtered after triturated with water. It was washed several times with hot water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (1.96 g, 58%), m.p. 134° (Found: S, 29.86. $C_{12}H_8N_4S_3O$ requires: S, 30.0%); ν_{max} 2 900 (CH₂), 1 710 (C=O) and 1 630 cm^{-1} .

3-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')mercaptomethyl]-6-benzylidenethiazolo[2,3-c]-s-triazol-5-one (5b): A mixture of **5a** (1.2 g), benzaldehyde (0.21 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed slowly for 4 h. After cooling, the solution was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting yellow solid was recrystallised from ethanol (0.86 g, 56%), m.p. 145° (Found: S, 23.49. $C_{16}H_{12}N_4OS_3$ requires: S, 23.52%); ν_{max} 1 680 (C=O), 1 580 and 1 400 cm^{-1} .

The *p*-chlorobenzylidene derivative (**5c**) was prepared from **5a** (0.6 g) and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.15 g) by following the above procedure and finally recrystallised from ethanol (0.53 g, 65%), m.p. 196° (Found: S, 21.72. $C_{19}H_{11}N_4S_3OCl$ requires: S, 21.69%); ν_{max} 3 350br (NH) and 1 710 cm^{-1} (C=O).

3-[S-(Benzothiazolyl-2')mercaptomethyl]-6-dimethylaminomethylthiazolo[2,3-c]-s-triazol-5-one (6d): A mixture of **5a** (0.8 g), dimethylamine (3 ml) and formalin (3 ml) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed till everything went into the solution. Then 2N HCl (2 drops) was added and the reflux continued for another 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the gummy

material was kept in contact with ammonia overnight during which a crystalline solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (0.5 g, 56%), m.p. 207° (Found: S, 25.13. $C_{15}H_{14}N_2S_2O$ requires: S, 25.46%).

The diethylaminomethyl derivative (6e) was prepared from 5a and diethylamine by following the above procedure and was recrystallised from ethanol (0.8 g, 54%), m.p. 218° (Found: S, 23.73. $C_{17}H_{19}N_2S_2O$ requires: S, 23.70%); ν_{max} 2950, 1750 (C=O) and 1630 cm^{-1} .

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